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The Impact of Webcare Quality on Buying Behaviour: A Study in Çanakkale¹

Webcare Kalitesinin Satın Alma Davranışına Etkisi: Çanakkale İlinde Bir Araştırma

ÖZET

The increasing share of e-commerce in global trade in the 20th century has not only created new opportunities for businesses but also brought new problems and solutions. The rapid spread of e-commerce both in Turkey and the world, especially during the Covid19 pandemic period, has led businesses to take part in the digital world. Businesses that have to keep up with the digital world also have to perform functions such as sales, marketing and customer service management in the e-commerce world with new methods. Customer experience and product reviews, which have become an important element in e-commerce, have led to the concept of webcare. The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of webcare, which has become an important element, especially in e-commerce activities, on consumers' purchasing behavior. In the research, the young population, ages between 18-25, who use e-commerce more often and whose digital literacy is higher than other generations, are selected as the sample. Data is collected through surveys from 354 participants in Çanakkale province. In the study using quantitative analysis methods, the webcare quality scale (Ghosh and Mandal, 2020) is translated into Turkish and evaluated by factor analysis, and the relationship between webcare quality and purchasing behavior is subjected to correlation and regression analyses. Research findings show that Webcare quality is divided into 5 dimensions in participant perceptions and that these dimensions have a positive relationship with purchasing behavior. Regression analysis findings show that especially in webcare quality, the reliability dimension, which includes coherence, assurance and retention dimensions originally, is effective on purchasing behavior. The findings also reveal that consumers follow business responses at a very high rate when it comes to webcare, and most of this following happens on the e-commerce platform where the purchase occurs. The study is completed with comments and suggestions regarding the findings.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Customer Service Management, E-Commerce, Webcare, Consumer Behavior, Digital Marketing.

ABSTRACT

20. yüzyılda e-ticaretin küresel ticaret içerisindeki artan payı işletmeler için yeni fırsatlar yarattığı kadar yeni sorunları ve çözümleri de beraberinde getirmiştir. E-ticaretin özellikle Covid19 pandemi döneminde hem Türkiye’de hem de dünyada hızla yaygınlaşması işletmeleri dijital dünyada yer almaya yöneltmiştir. Dijital dünyaya ayak uydurmak zorunda kalan işletmeler de e-ticaret dünyasında satış, pazarlama, müşteri hizmetleri yönetimi gibi fonksiyonlarını yeni yöntemlerle gerçekleştirmek durumundadır. E-ticarete önemli bir unsur haline gelen müşteri deneyimi ve ürün yorumları webcare kavramını ortaya çıkarmıştır. Bu çalışmanın amacı özellikle e-ticaret faaliyetlerinde önemli bir unsur haline gelen webcare’in tüketicilerin satın alma davranışlarına olan etkisi incelemektir. Araştırmada örneklem olarak e-ticareti daha yoğunlukla kullanan ve dijital okuryazarlığı diğer kuşaklara göreceli olarak daha yüksek olan 18-25 yaş arası gençler örneklem olarak belirlenmiştir. Çanakkale ilinde 354 katılımcıdan anketler aracılığı ile veri toplanmıştır. Nicel analiz yöntemleri kullanılan çalışmada webcare kalitesi ölçeği (Ghosh ve Mandal, 2020) Türkçe’ye çevrilerek faktör analizi ile değerlendirilmekte, webcare kalitesinin satın alma davranışı ile ilişkisi korelasyon ve regresyon analizlerine tabi tutulmaktadır. Araştırma bulguları Webcare kalitesinin katılımcı algılarında 5 boyuta ayrıldığını ve bu boyutların satın alma davranışı ile pozitif yönlü bir ilişkiye sahip olduğunu göstermektedir. Regresyon analizleri özellikle webcare kalitesinde tutarlılık, güven ve müşteriye elde tutmayı kapsayan güvenilirlik boyutunun satın alma davranışları üzerinde etkili olduğunu göstermektedir. Bulgular ayrıca tüketicilerin webcare kapsamında işletme yanıtlarını çok yüksek oranda takip ettiğini ve bu takibin büyük bölümünün satın almanın gerçekleştiği e-ticaret platformunda olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Çalışma bulgulara yönelik yorumlar ve öneriler ile tamamlanmaktadır.

Keywords: Müşteri Hizmetleri Yönetimi, E-Ticaret, Webcare, Tüketici Davranışları, Dijital Pazarlama.

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1. INTRODUCTION

As e-commerce entered people's daily lives, consumers' shopping experiences began to differ. Consumers, who have to use their physical strength and time to meet their shopping needs now can devote their energy and time to other daily activities, thanks to e-commerce. There are also different alternatives that online shopping offers to consumers. Advantages such as easily finding the product you are looking for, being able to shop without going out, and comparing the best and most affordable products on different platforms can be listed. Of course, although this situation offers advantages such as time, energy and convenience, it also brings with it individual problems such as laziness in daily life or addiction to shopping. However, as the importance of time increases for people, the importance of these disadvantages will decrease and their solutions will also improve. Various benefits of e-commerce for businesses can be listed. The human resources required for the activities of businesses are decreasing, the need for financial investment for different branches and stores is eliminated, and fixed and variable costs such as rent, invoices, store layout, etc., apart from human resources, are decreasing at a high rate. Due to these advantages, businesses are increasingly turning to digitalization and operating in the digital world (Özdemir, 2023:144). Instead of these costs, businesses face variable costs such as logistics costs that arise when sales are made. Apart from such advantages thanks to e-commerce, there are various issues that businesses should not ignore in order to ensure their sustainability on these platforms. In particular, customer satisfaction must be kept at a high level in order to retain customers and increase the number of existing customers. At this point, consumers who have an online shopping experience can make a complaint to the businesses in question when they encounter any negative situation. The quality of webcare conceptualized in this regard should be taken into consideration precisely here.

2. E-COMMERCE

E-commerce first started to take off in the USA in the late 1970s, through the expansion of the Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) system, as the cost of establishing a business was high and the establishment of a business required effort for smaller businesses. By expanding this data system, electronic access to commercial information became possible after 1987 (Çetin, 2014:67). As the internet has increasingly reached more areas, commerce has also taken its share and the idea of "Electronic Commerce", in short e-commerce, has been put forward. Today trade can be defined as establishment of e-commerce services and products via the Internet and telecommunication networks; it can be stated as the realization of advertising, sales, and distribution (Bedestenci and Canitez, 2012:434).

Internet-based electronic business can be defined as a system that provides an environment for businesses to communicate with customers, business partners, employees and suppliers via the Internet, external networks and intranets. The internal and external connection of the electronic business enables companies to be more beneficial by reducing costs, increasing productivity and achieving business goals faster (Beheshti and Salehi-Sangari, 2007:234). As can be understood from the definitions, the concept of e-commerce is not a very new concept, but when the internet environment is considered in terms of product, and the market area it addresses, e-commerce differs from regular commerce because it is global.

The proliferation of online shopping is encouraging widespread research aimed at attracting and retaining consumers from a consumer or technology-focused perspective. The consumer-focused perspective focuses on consumers' distinct beliefs about online shopping. Such beliefs can influence purchasing channel choice. For example, online consumer behavior is examined from the perspectives of consumer demographics, cognitive/psychological characteristics, risk and benefit perceptions of online shopping, shopping motivation and shopping orientation (Zhou et al., 2007: 41). While virtual shopping brought additional income to many companies, it also caused many companies to close their businesses.

Being a social being, humans are affected by everything that happens around them. The internet, which entered our lives many years ago, has become an indispensable element over time. As internet use becomes more widespread, the level of benefit from it also increases. The internet, which was previously used in areas such as exchanging information, researching and communicating, has also shifted to different areas. For example, the role of the internet in daily life has increased in meeting the needs of the individual to continue his life. Especially the Covid 19 pandemic experienced around the world confirms this situation. Nowadays, shopping can be done without leaving home, making one's life easier in this way. The internet, which brings the distance closer, will continue to offer different opportunities for humanity day by day. Of course, it would be insufficient to think only about the individual in the internet environment. Considering that businesses offer online shopping, this is important for both parties. Businesses need to pay attention to some factors in order to maintain and maintain their presence on this platform. Factors such as ensuring

customer continuity, maintaining the effectiveness and efficiency of the brand, and keeping the brand image at a high level can be given as examples. Achieving customer satisfaction after shopping can be taken into consideration in creating customer continuity in online shopping.

3. WEBCARE

Internet-driven technologies and the effects of how consumers search for products/services, evaluate, purchase, and then share their consumption experiences with other consumers have spurred a wave of change in the way they interact with brands (Ghosh, 2017:148). Providing consumers' post-purchase feedback online has enabled brands to take consumer feedback into account and see it as valuable. This shift is often referred to as webcare, defined as 'the act of engaging with complaining consumers online by actively searching the web to address consumer feedback (e.g. questions, concerns and complaints)' (Ghosh and Mandal,2020: 1557).

Several service failure incidents are published daily on different types of online channels such as company websites, third-party complaint sites, and social media. These messages have harmful effects. It can significantly damage the brand image. It can also lead to other negative consequences such as decreased brand attitude, low purchase intention, and low product trial rates (Ghosh and Mandal, 2020: 1556-1557). To reduce these harmful effects, many companies monitor and respond to the flow of negative reviews through webcare, defined as "the act of engaging complaining consumers online by actively searching the web to address consumer feedback" (Ghosh and Raju,2018: 2).

Webcare is performed by one or more company representatives and serves as a tool to support customer relations, reputation and brand management (Van Noort and Willemsen, 2011:133). The concept of Webcare is a concept that brings benefits to companies in terms of gaining customers and regaining lost customers. It ensures customer continuity for the business.

The concept of webcare is a message from marketers to consumers, and one of the most important features of webcare is that it increases the repurchase intention of consumers who are dissatisfied after the purchasing behavior by making them forgive the brand (Kuşat, 2022: 21). It shows that higher levels of consumer forgiveness further motivate complaining consumers to strengthen consumer-brand relationships and ultimately provide the gift of unconditional acceptance. This trend is reflected in satisfaction with webcare, positive brand attitudes and purchase intentions (Ghosh and Raju, 2018: 241). Webcare allows them to change the course of the purchasing and sales relationship (Chen and Wu, 2021: 20). Research shows that appropriate webcare can lead to positive brand-related reactions among complaining customers, including positive brand evaluations and increased customer loyalty and satisfaction (Weitzl and Hutzinger, 2017: 164).

The concept of Webcare is important not only for companies in the private sector but also for public institutions and organizations. Webcare management in the public sector has been approached from a different perspective compared to the private sector, and political risks have also been taken into account. With Webcare, the opinions of the country's citizens are consulted in determining public services (Kuşat, 2022:21).

4. METHODOLOGY

This study aims to examine how webcare quality impacts consumers' purchasing behavior. In this context, webcare dimensions are the dependent variable, while purchasing behavior is examined as the independent variable. Generalizable findings are presented using quantitative research methods. Data is obtained from a total of 354 participants from the sample, mostly through an online survey, using a 5-point Likert scale. The data collected from these surveys is subjected to factor analysis, correlation analysis and regression analysis through the SPSS program.

The research is especially important for businesses operating in e-commerce in order to retain existing customers, ensure customer satisfaction, keep the brand image at a high level, and ensure higher customer continuity compared to other businesses in their market area. A company that corrects a faulty situation in a friendly, sincere and convincing manner towards its own customers gains respect in the eyes of other buyers. The concept of webcare, which is examined in the study, is an issue that especially businesses should pay attention to. It is expected that paying attention to the benefits of this concept in the Internet age will be beneficial for businesses.

The hypotheses established within the scope of the research are expressed below.

H1: There is a positive relationship between Webcare quality and purchasing behavior.

The population of this research consists of consumers who carry out e-commerce. As a sample, consumers in Çanakkale who are over 18 years old and have an online shopping experience are determined. The majority of the sample includes students. The reason for this is that there is a larger student group in the area where the survey was conducted.

As a data collection tool, a survey consisting of demographic questions, webcare quality scale, and purchasing behavior scale is used in the study. The survey method was chosen because it was determined that it would be much faster and more useful in terms of reaching more participants. The webcare quality scale in the survey form was included in the survey from the study of authors Ghosh, T. and Mandal, S. (2020). Purchasing behavior is measured with a three-item scale. The number of surveys collected was 354 and all of them were included in the analysis.

4.1. Demographic Findings

In the data collection tool used in the study, participants are asked about their gender, the frequency of making positive comments, the frequency of making negative comments, on which platforms they commented after their purchases, and whether they read the business responses to their comments. Data and findings regarding these statements are seen in Tables 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 below.

Table 1. Gender Statistics of Participants

Gender	Frequency	Percent(%)
Female	227	64,3
Male	125	35,4
Total	352	99,7

As seen in Table 1 above, 64% of the participants are women and 35% are men. Two participants did not indicate their gender. It can be stated that consumers have a balanced distribution in terms of gender.

Table 2. Rate of Positive Comments

Rate of Positive Comments	Frequency	Percent (%)
Never	74	21,0
Sometimes	115	32,6
Often	48	13,6
Mostly	70	19,8
Always	45	12,7
Total	353	100,0

As can be seen above in Table 2 shows frequencies of positive comments of participants after a purchase in the context of e-commerce. Findings shows that only 12,7% of consumers always comment after a purchase and 21% of consumers never post positive comments after a purchase.

Table 3. Rate of Negative Comments

Rate of Negative Comments	Frequency	Percent (%)
Never	64	18,1
Sometimes	124	35,1
Often	51	14,4
Mostly	57	16,1
Always	55	15,6
Total	351	99,4

As can be seen above in Table 3 shows frequencies of negative comments of participants after a purchase in the context of e-trade. Findings shows that 15,6% of consumers always comment after a purchase and 18,1% of consumers never post negative comments after a purchase.

Table 4. Reading Business Replies to Comments

Reading Replies	Frequency	Percent (%)
Yes	331	93,8
No	20	5,7
Total	353	100,0

As can be seen above in Table 4 93,8% of consumers read the replies of businesses to their comments. This shows that activities regarding webcare indeed reach the intended audience.

Table 5. Customers' Choice of Platforms for Comments

Customers' Choice of Platforms for Comments	Frequency	Percent (%)
Social Media Page of Store	31	8,8
General Social Media	15	4,2
General Complaint Platforms	46	13,0
Official Channels	9	2,5
E-Commerce Platform used to purchase	251	71,1
Total	353	100,0

As can be seen above in Table 5 71,1% of consumers use the e-commerce platform which they have used to make the purchase for positive/negative comments. Only 2,5% of consumers reach out to official channels to comment about their purchase. 13% of consumers use platforms created for complaints.

4.2. Factor Analysis

Webcare quality scale (Ghosh and Mandal, 2017) is translated into Turkish by authors, to check the perceptions of Turkish populations and to determine the validity and reliability of the scale, factor analysis is used in the study. It is determined that performing factor analysis will prevent the difficulties regarding relationships between variables in multivariate statistical analysis. The analysis is performed with direct oblimin rotation and the findings can be seen below in Table 6 and 7.

Table 6. KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		,948
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	6711,123
	df	465
	Sig.	,000
Total Variance Explained	7 Components	% 70,931

As seen in Table 6 below, the KMO Bartlett value was obtained as 0.948 in the factor analysis with varimax rotation. In line with this result, it seems that the research sample is sufficient to conduct factor analysis. Looking at the sphericity test result, it is seen that a factor analysis is viable. Also, the 7 components explain almost 71% of the collected data.

Table 7. Factor Analysis via Oblimin Rotation

Statements/Dimensions	Reliability(Assurance, Retention, Coherence)	Elaborateness	Immediacy	Buying Behaviour	Ownership	Civility	Personalisation
Retention3	,860						
Retention4	,718						
Retention2	,684						
Coherence4	,667						
Coherence1	,634						
Coherence3	,628						
Assurance2	,628						
Coherence2	,602						
Assurance4	,594						
Assurance3	,534						
Civility4	,500						
Elaborateness2		,832					
Elaborateness1		,672					
Elaborateness3		,501					
Immediacy1			-,791				
Immediacy2			-,760				
Immediacy3			-,645				
Immediacy4			-,610				
Ownership1			-,575				
Buying Behaviour2				,901			
Buying Behaviour1				,844			
Buying Behaviour3				,727			
Ownership2					,792		
Ownership3					,781		
Civility3						,711	
Civility4						,668	
Civility2						,546	
Assurance1						,536	
Personalisation2							-,703
Personalisation4							-,695
Personalisation1							-,607
Cronbach α	0,945	0,772	0,859	0,810	0,814	0,744	0,809

This matrix examines the relationship between 7 factors and 31 statements. The lower limit of factor loadings between the factors and the questions used was determined as >0.5 in this study. 9 statements of the webcare quality scale are removed because of low factor loadings and superimposition. These statements are ownership4, ownership5, comprehensiveness1, comprehensiveness2, comprehensiveness3, civility1, retention1, personalisation3, personalisation5. After removing the low factor loadings and solving superimposition webcare quality is divided into 6 dimensions. It can be seen that statements of coherence, assurance, and retention merged into a new dimension which is defined as reliability. Table 7 also shows Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficients of dimensions, which are the dimensions of the scale used in the research: Reliability, Elaborateness, Immediacy, Ownership, Civility, Personalisation and Buying behavior. According to the data, it is seen that all Cronbach α coefficients are above 0.7 and therefore all dimensions are reliable. It can be stated that the scale is valid and reliable, considering the findings at this stage.

4.3. Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Analysis

After the factor analysis descriptive statistics of the data are checked. To test the hypothesis of the study, Pearson correlation analysis is performed. Descriptive statistics can be seen below in Table 8.

Table 8. Descriptive statistics

	N Statistic	Mean Statistic	Descriptive Statistics		Skewness		Kurtosis	
			Std. Deviation Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error	
Reliability	353	4,3806	,67416	-1,732	,130	4,812	,259	
Elaborateness	353	3,9372	,85663	-,713	,130	,556	,259	
Immediacy	353	4,3258	,73688	-1,942	,130	5,383	,259	
Buying Behaviour	352	4,2093	,87312	-1,325	,130	1,933	,259	
Ownership	353	3,7790	1,08419	-,744	,130	-,059	,259	
Civility	353	4,0286	,76314	-,979	,130	1,650	,259	
Personalization	353	4,1780	,86977	-1,223	,130	1,534	,259	
Valid N (listwise)	352							

As can be seen above in Table 8 skewness and kurtosis of the collected data reveals issues about quantitative methods but since the sample consists of more than 350 people these problems can be neglected.

Table 9. Correlation Analysis

		Correlations						
		Reliability	Elaborateness	Immediacy	Ownership	Civility	Personalisation	Buying Behaviour
Reliability	Pearson Correlation	1	,570**	,709**	,412**	,641**	,616**	,586**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000
	N	353	353	353	353	353	353	352
Elaborateness	Pearson Correlation	,570**	1	,538**	,443**	,558**	,568**	,345**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000		,000	,000	,000	,000	,000
	N	353	353	353	353	353	353	352
Immediacy	Pearson Correlation	,709**	,538**	1	,477**	,566**	,521**	,471**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000		,000	,000	,000	,000
	N	353	353	353	353	353	353	352
Ownership	Pearson Correlation	,412**	,443**	,477**	1	,474**	,334**	,258**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000		,000	,000	,000
	N	353	353	353	353	353	353	352
Civility	Pearson Correlation	,641**	,558**	,566**	,474**	1	,575**	,362**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000	,000		,000	,000
	N	353	353	353	353	353	353	352
Personalisation	Pearson Correlation	,616**	,568**	,521**	,334**	,575**	1	,414**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000		,000
	N	353	353	353	353	353	353	352
Buying Behaviour	Pearson Correlation	,586**	,345**	,471**	,258**	,362**	,414**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	
	N	352	352	352	352	352	352	352

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As can be seen above in Table 9 correlation analysis supports H1. There is a medium level positive correlation between reliability and buying behavior (,589) and the relationship is significant at the ,01 level ($p=,000$). There is a medium level positive correlation between elaborateness and buying behavior (,345) and the relationship is significant at the ,01 level ($p=,000$). There is a medium level positive correlation between immediacy and buying behavior (,471) and the relationship is significant at the ,01 level ($p=,000$).

There is a low level positive correlation between ownership and buying behavior (.258) and the relationship is significant at the .01 level ($p=,000$). There is a medium level positive correlation between civility and buying behavior (.362) and the relationship is significant at the .01 level ($p=,000$). There is a medium level positive correlation between personalisation and buying behavior (.589) and the relationship is significant at the .01 level ($p=,000$).

4.4. Regression Analysis

After testing the hypothesis via correlation analysis, data is subjected to regression analysis for further examination. A linear regression model is used to examine the impact of webcare dimensions on buying behaviour. The findings of the regression analysis model can be seen below in Tables 10, 11 and 12.

Table 10. Regression Analysis Model Summary

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			
						F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	,597 ^a	,356	,345	,70671	,356	31,795	6	345	,000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Personalization, Ownership, Immediacy, Elaborateness, Civility, Reliability

As it can be seen above in Table 10 the adjusted R square of the model is 0,345 and this shows that the webcare explains an important part of buying behaviour.

Table 11. Regression Analysis Anova

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	95,277	6	15,879	31,795	,000 ^b
	Residual	172,306	345	,499		
	Total	267,583	351			

a. Dependent Variable: Buying Behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Personalization, Ownership, Immediacy, Elaborateness, Civility, Reliability

As can be seen above in Table 11 regression model regarding the hypothesis is statistically significant and the model works.

Table 12. Regression Analysis Coefficient Values

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	,769	,261		2,943	,003		
	Reliability	,647	,092	,500	7,046	,000	,371	2,696
	Elaborateness	-,019	,060	-,019	-,322	,748	,537	1,862
	Immediacy	,133	,077	,112	1,720	,086	,440	2,275
	Ownership	,008	,042	,010	,183	,855	,690	1,449
	Civility	-,081	,072	-,071	-1,136	,257	,479	2,089
	Personalization	,097	,060	,097	1,616	,107	,524	1,910

a. Dependent Variable: Buying Behaviour

As can be seen above in Table 12 the only dimension that shows a statistically significant impact in the regression model is the reliability dimension ($p=,000$). The B value of reliability dimension is ,647.

According to these findings it can be said that webcare, especially reliability dimension of webcare, has a significant impact on the buying behaviour of consumers.

5. CONCLUSION

Nowadays, it is undeniable that the internet is an indispensable feature and the opportunity to benefit from it has increased. It is observed that the number of people using e-commerce to meet their daily needs has increased can be seen in many conducted studies after the Covid19 pandemic. The ease of e-commerce, fast shopping, and many shopping alternatives attract consumers. Such advantages may attract consumers to shop online. Of course there are many factors to consider regarding the disadvantages of online shopping. Examples include sending incomplete or faulty products, not having an immediate contact person for the consumer in case of any faulty product shipment, problems in reaching the consumer regarding the product/service (such as delay in cargo).

In light of all these explanations, most businesses focus on consumers' attitudes and behaviors while shopping online and carry out studies on these. This study was conducted to examine the effect of webcare quality on consumer purchasing behavior.

The data collected in the study shows that consumers read business responses to their comments within the scope of webcare at a very high rate (93.8%). In other words, consumers read and care about the responses given by businesses to their comments. The majority of consumers make positive or negative comments at varying frequencies. Most of these comments occur on the e-commerce platform where the purchase took place. In other words, consumers look for the first solution to their problems at the place of purchase. This finding is important in terms of which channel businesses should focus their webcare quality efforts on first.

Factor analysis in the research shows the problems of the webcare quality scale in the Turkish sample. Despite the high number of participants, low factor loadings and overlapping factor loading problems were observed in the scale, and 9 statements had to be excluded from the analysis for the data set that could work in a multivariate analysis. Studies in this direction can be carried out for the reliability and validity of the scale in the Turkish sample. As a result of the correlation analysis, significant correlation values are observed within the scope of webcare, especially between reliability, immediacy and personalization and purchasing. Further analysis reveals that the reliability variable has a significant impact on buying behavior.

When evaluated in terms of recommendations to be given to the business world, businesses and managers should take into account that consumers follow and care about activities related to webcare quality. Especially considering its impact on purchasing behavior, the work to be done within the scope of webcare will have a direct impact on the sales success and revenues of the business.

In future research, it would be meaningful to investigate the effects of webcare quality on brand-related variables of the business. Purchasing behavior is a variable focused on short-term impact in businesses, and business elements such as brand awareness, brand perception, and brand image that explain long-term benefits and variables can be considered as important variables related to webcare.

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